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D2.2 Publishing workflow enriched FDOs to EOSC

Work Package 2

Technical References

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Executive Summary

The concept of publishing workflows as scholarly is being recognised and practiced through repositories like WorkflowHub and principles for FAIR Computational Workflow. This deliverable describes how the evolving landscape of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) can facilitate workflow publishing in a federated and distributed manner, exemplified by how workflows for Galaxy are published.

List of Abbreviations

- **ARCP:** Archive and Packaging
- **DOI:** Digital Object Identifier
- **EEN:** EOSC EU Node
- **EOSC:** European Open Science Cloud
- **FAIR:** Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability
- **Galaxy CoDex:** Galaxy Communities Dock
- **GTN:** Galaxy Training Network
- **IWC:** Galaxy's Intergalactic Workflow Commission
- **KG:** Knowledge Graph
- **NFDI:** Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur
- **OpenAIRE:** Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
- **ORCID:** Open Researcher and Contributor ID
- **ORD:** Open Research Data
- **PID:** Persistent Identifier
- **RO:** Research Object
- **RI:** Research Infrastructure
- **TRL:** Technology readiness level
- **URI:** Uniform Resource Identifier
- **WRROC:** Workflow Run RO-Crate

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Catalogues in EOSC

EOSC Marketplace

As part of the initial establishment of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), EOSC Enhance (and later EOSC Core and EOSC Future) built the *EOSC Marketplace* as part of the *EOSC Portal* [Appleton 2019] (or EOSC Exchange). The marketplace provided a listing of EOSC services, publications, and later datasets, training materials and interoperability guidelines (Figure 1).

The content of the marketplace was registered from an *onboarded provider* [Ševkušić 2023], which would need to satisfy requirements such as being a legal entity, agreeing to the EOSC principles and providing governance information such as helpdesk and technology readiness level (TRL) of registered services.

Figure 1: EOSC Marketplace <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/> in 2024 ([archived 2024-03-01](#))

Later, the Marketplace developed further the concept of a *data provider* and added APIs for automated registration of data source content, following the [EOSC Data Source Profile](#) and related [EOSC Portal Profiles](#).

EOSC Future developed these profiles into the EOSC Data Model (Figure 2) and expanded on the types of research products, including publications, data, software; as well as workflows and protocols (which arguably are hybrids of publications, data and software).

Figure 2: EOSC Data Model, reproduced from EOSC Future [Research Product Profile](#)

This revised model builds on the OpenAIRE Guidelines e.g. for [Institutional and Thematic Repositories](#).

As of 2024-04, the marketplace at <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/> was made read-only and the following month decommissioned. The purpose for this change was to prepare a snapshot of its content, in preparation for the transition to the [procured EOSC EU Node services](#) which had been tasked to develop the next evolution of the EOSC marketplace.

EuroScienceGateway in EOSC Marketplace

The two main services of EuroScienceGateway, [Galaxy Europe](#) and [WorkflowHub](#), were registered early 2022 in the EOSC Marketplace. WorkflowHub was initially registered as an EOSC service provided by ELIXIR-UK [Goble 2023], with Earlham Institute serving as the legal entity behind ELIXIR-UK. The European Galaxy Server was registered as an EOSC service provided by University of Freiburg.

As part of EuroScienceGateway, we improved these EOSC Marketplace registrations. WorkflowHub, being recognised as a registry/repository of research outputs, was changed to be a *data source* and was also affiliated with the ELIXIR Europe provider. Additional governance details such as [data retention policies](#) and funding were provided for both entries.

We explored routes to publish Galaxy training material and WorkflowHub registration directly to the EOSC Marketplace through the use of data provider APIs.

OpenAIRE Explore & Graph

[OpenAIRE](#) operates e-infrastructure services for Open Science in the EU, encouraging and supporting open scholarly communication. OpenAIRE is providing several [scholarly communication services for EOSC](#).

[OpenAIRE Explore](#) catalogues research outputs including publication, data, software and research grants, gathered from a multitude of sources. While a large part of OpenAIRE is aggregating metadata, it also performs identifier deduplication and infer linkage, e.g. to inform EC reporting for a grant (Figure 3).

The [Zenodo](#) open research repository is general purpose for any researcher, and the metadata of Zenodo deposits form a large part of the [OpenAIRE Graph](#), the scholarly knowledge graph that backs OpenAIRE Explore. The graph can be accessed [programmatically](#) (e.g. queries) or [downloaded](#) as a JSON-based dataset.

The OpenAIRE graph and its downloads uses a common [data model](#) that includes [Research products](#) such as Publications, Data, Software or [others](#) (e.g. lecture, film, physical object, sound, model research activity, and research object). Attributes include *mainTitle, authors, contributors, PIDs, publisher, and formats*.

Figure 3: [OpenAIRE Explore listing](#) of EuroScienceGateway project outputs (e.g. deliverable and publications)

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EuroScienceGateway and OpenAIRE

OpenAIRE and EuroScienceGateway have signed a [memorandum of understanding](#) to collaborate on increasing the FAIRness of research outputs from Galaxy. As part of this effort, the [Zenodo integration](#) has been completed, enabling Galaxy to search directly within Zenodo and import data. Additionally, Galaxy [can export](#) RO-Crates to Zenodo while handling DOIs appropriately, including the workspace [history](#). Furthermore, Galaxy Communities Dock ([Galaxy CoDex](#)) serves as a resource hub for the Galaxy community, linking tools, packages, containers, training materials, and workflows with the ELIXIR tools ecosystem through a weekly updated [catalog](#). This catalog facilitates seamless ingestion into the OpenAIRE Knowledge Graph (KG), further enhancing accessibility and interoperability.

EOSC EU Node Resource Hub

In 2024-10, EOSC [launched](#) the [EOSC EU Node](#) (EEN which adds services like file synchronisation, interactive notebooks and cloud containers).

The EEN includes a redeveloped [Resource Hub](#) that builds on the idea of the EOSC Marketplace (Figure 4). As a starting point, the entries from the Marketplace were transitioned over to the Resource Hub, following GDPR approval from each provider.

An equivalent onboarding process as in EOSC Future is being drafted, but as of 2025-02 is not yet active. The transitioned list of Services and Data Sources are largely static, however the aggregated entries of publications, data and software are updated from their upstream sources like [DataCite](#) (Figure 4).

The focus of the new EOSC EU Node has been on the computational [services](#), which include a predefined *Tool* that deploy Galaxy on the node's Kubernetes cluster. Individual users may choose to spin up a separate Galaxy server in this way, e.g. to explore use of private data or to customise its tool installation. Although this is not typically how Galaxy is meant to be used for research, this can still be beneficial for training purposes.

Equivalent tool definitions for other workflow systems that are more command-line based, like Nextflow and Snakemake, may be beneficial for future execution capabilities of the WorkflowHub. The EEN already includes a Notebook offering, and several Jupyter notebooks are registered as workflows in WorkflowHub.

In terms of publishing workflows in EOSC, being able to link to such execution methods can be a powerful way to “wake up” workflow deposits, as any EU-based researcher will receive a free compute/storage “credits” on the EEN.

As of 2025-02 the EEN is not listing a public API or a system of permalinks for such activation (e.g. equivalent to the [“Run in Galaxy”](#) button), manual navigation and container deployment in the EU Node user interface is currently necessary. This can be a significant barrier for tighter integration with WorkflowHub or Galaxy, as most of its users are not yet

familiar with the EOSC EU Node and the technical level of Kubernetes container deployment is deeper than the abstraction levels that experienced workflow authors commonly work at.

Contrasting with the earlier EOSC Marketplace idea, there is a general trend in EOSC EU Node’s Resource Hub towards aggregation rather than registration, following the model of OpenAIRE, to combine the EU Node’s core services with research outputs and offerings from the emerging regional and thematic EOSC nodes.

The screenshot shows the EOSC Resource Hub interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with tabs for 'All resources', 'Publications', 'Data', 'Software', 'Other Products', 'Services', 'Data Sources', 'Training', 'Interoperability Guidelines', and 'Tools'. The 'Software' tab is selected. Below the navigation bar, there are filter options for 'Access right', 'Publication date', and 'Funder', all of which are currently expanded. A search filter 'Showing 1 to 20 of 5,861 resources' is visible. A dropdown menu for 'Relevance' is set to 'Relevance'. The search results are displayed in a list format. The first result is titled 'NorwegianVeterinaryInstitute/Nepal: Release of the update Nepal pipeline.' and includes details such as 'Year: 2024', 'Views: 0', 'Downloads: 0', 'Citations: 0', 'Author: Thomas H.A. Haverkamp', 'Publisher: ZENODO', and 'Identifier: 10.5281/zenodo.10821960 (DOI) | 10.5281/zenodo.10821961 (DOI)'. A 'Cite' button is present below the identifier. The second result is titled 'Repeat masking - TSI' and includes details such as 'Year: 2024', 'Views: 0', 'Downloads: 0', 'Citations: 0', 'Author: Silver, Luke | Syme, Anna', and 'Identifier: 10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.875.3 (DOI) | 10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.875.2 (DOI)'. A 'Cite' button is also present below the identifier.

Figure 4: [Search](#) for “workflow” in EOSC Resource Hub includes WorkflowHub entries registered in DataCite.

EuroScienceGateway and the EOSC EU Node

The EOSC EU Node has been [explored by EuroScienceGateway](#) for use of its computational capabilities to assist Galaxy execution, by using the EEN cloud offering as a Pulsar node.

The service registrations for the [European Galaxy Server](#) and [WorkflowHub](#) has been transitioned to the EEN, but has as of 2025-02 not been updated since the Marketplace snapshot. A significant amount of service metadata, such as governance and TRL level, is no longer visible in the EEN listing. We recommend moving this to a structured documentation, but it should ideally also be machine-readable as FAIR metadata, e.g. in a corresponding [FAIRsharing entry](#).

[Workflow RO-Crate](#), the packaging and metadata method used by WorkflowHub (see [D2.1](#)) is listed as an Interoperability Guideline in the EOSC ResourceHub. This guideline will need to be updated to reflect later RO-Crate profile development.

The new federated shape of EOSC

The EOSC EU Node is the first bit of a new federated architecture of EOSC (Figure 5). This transition is inspired by ELIXIR Europe and large European Research Infrastructures, and recognises that “EOSC” will not be a centralised technical offering, but rather a gathering of interoperable infrastructures with common goals such as Open Science practices or FAIR sharing.

Figure 5: EOSC Federation Architecture composes multiple nodes at national or regional level, combined with domain-specific thematic nodes. The EOSC EU Node is aggregating based on federating capabilities, but the nodes may also communicate directly following the EOSC Interoperability Framework and EOSC interoperability guidelines. Reproduced from [EOSC 2024].

The EOSC Federation Handbook [EOSC 2024] is being developed, and details the structure of EOSC Nodes and the process for becoming a node. Becoming an EOSC Node is a significant undertaking, with [requirements](#) such as being a legal entity, quality service provisioning, third-party onboarding, EOSC core contributions and compliance with EOSC

rules. This should not be considered equivalent to the lightweight onboarding of “providers” in the initial marketplace, although some large providers may choose to become EOSC nodes in their own right.

The structure of EOSC Nodes have been inspired by the [ELIXIR Europe’s national nodes](#) and [commissioned services](#), to the extent that the EOSC Federation Handbook was derived from the [ELIXIR Handbook of Operations](#) and received ongoing input from experienced ELIXIR leaders.

An EOSC node will largely be able to provide many of the same capabilities as exemplified by the EEN such as services and catalogues, but being more domain-specific (e.g. bioimaging data bank) or with higher usage capacity for approved/regional users without using EOSC credits (e.g. utilising national super-computing infrastructure).

Several applications to become an EEN are likely to appear realised in 2025, for instance national nodes (e.g. “EOSC Germany” could build on [NFDI](#) and Helmholtz), new thematic scientific clusters (e.g. “EOSC climate science” could build on [EOSC FAIR Ease](#), [ClimateAdapt4EOSC](#), [FAIR2ADAPT](#)) and existing thematic research infrastructures (e.g. “EOSC life science” building on ELIXIR Europe, Instruct-ERIC and EMBL).

It becomes clear that there will be significant overlap between some of these emerging nodes, making the interoperability aspect of EOSC crucial (Figure 5). However, as of 2025-02, the machine-readable aspect of EOSC Node federation is not specified in technical details, and nodes are free to choose any method that follows the EOSC Interoperability Framework.

EuroScienceGateway in federated EOSC

Both WorkflowHub and the European Galaxy Server already fit in multiple potential EOSC nodes, but are likely not large enough to become EOSC nodes in their own right. While registration in the EOSC Marketplace just needed “any” legal entity to be responsible for the registration, requirements for operating an EOSC node comes with significant responsibilities.

For instance, the WorkflowHub server is currently physically hosted by The University of Manchester, is a registered [ELIXIR UK service](#), which by ELIXIR’s federation makes it an ELIXIR Europe service. It could become part of the offering of a national node (assuming the UK was allowed to apply), a thematic Research Infrastructure (RI) node for ELIXIR Europe, or a thematic node under the umbrella of life sciences. Yet the repository has many workflows from outside life sciences and outside the UK or EU.

The European Galaxy Server is in a similar pinch-point, as a large international collaborative initiative that mostly meet virtually, even if only considering the physical server hosting, these have multiple potential EOSC Nodes as “home”.

The Pulsar network is another strong alternative to the Kubernetes cloud offering of the EOSC Node. However, the Pulsar network itself is also federated, and it is difficult to pin down which region or science domain “owns” this network.

WorkflowHub and Datacite

WorkflowHub can register DataCite DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers). Workflow creators may assign a DOI to their workflow if it is registered on WorkflowHub and available to the public. Further DOIs may be assigned to subsequent versions of the workflow.

Metadata provided by workflow creators when registering or updating the workflow in WorkflowHub is incorporated into the DataCite DOI registration using the [DataCite Metadata Schema version 4](#). This means that once registered, the metadata is automatically incorporated into the [DataCite Commons PID Graph](#) and [OpenAIRE Research Graph \(example\)](#). These again feed workflow metadata into the current EOSC EU Node.

At the time of writing, DataCite lists 498 workflows and workflow versions published through WorkflowHub, with 37% growth in registrations from 2023 to 2024 (see figure 6).

Figure 6: Graph of WorkflowHub DOIs registered from 2021-2024.

The same metadata can also be used to generate an RO-Crate for a WorkflowHub workflow on demand.

These DOIs also have benefits for our work on building a knowledge graph (KG) using RO-Crates generated from all public workflows in WorkflowHub [reference [D2.1](#) & <https://github.com/workflowhub-eu/workflowhub-graph>]. Currently, RO-Crates are uniquely identified in the graph using ARCP [Soiland-Reyes 2018] identifiers, but this could be improved by using DOIs instead where they exist.

Workflow metadata in Galaxy

The quality of metadata that is fed into WorkflowHub can be improved by encouraging workflow creators to use linting tools which help the user to implement best practices. For example, the [planemo](#) SDK assists Galaxy workflow developers with following best practices for their workflow configuration and metadata. Improvements to [planemo](#) in the last year include ensuring authors are represented using their full ORCID URI rather than the shortened form (e.g. “<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1825-0097>” rather than “0000-0002-1825-0097”) (<https://github.com/galaxyproject/planemo/pull/1458>). This has the effect of improving the quality of the WorkflowHub/DataCite/OpenAIRE knowledge graphs, as it is easier to identify when the same author appears in multiple workflows or other works if the full URI is used.

Similar improvements have been done via the Graphical Workflow Best Practice Wizard in the Galaxy interface (Figure 7).

Best Practices Review

Try to automatically fix issues.

 This workflow is not annotated. Providing an annotation helps workflow executors understand the purpose and usage of the workflow.

 Annotate your Workflow.

 This workflow does not specify creator(s). This is important metadata for workflows that will be published and/or shared to help workflow executors know how to cite the workflow authors.

 Provide Creator Details.

 This workflow does not specify a license. This is important metadata for workflows that will be published and/or shared to help workflow executors understand how it may be used.

 Specify a License.

 Workflow parameters are using formal input parameters.

 All non-optional inputs to workflow steps are connected to formal input parameters.

 Some workflow inputs are missing labels and/or annotations:

 Input dataset collection: Missing a label and annotation

 NC_045512: Missing an annotation

 The following workflow outputs have no labels, they should be assigned a useful label or unchecked in the workflow editor to mark them as no longer being a workflow output:

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/fastp/fastp/0.19.5+galaxy1: report_json

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/fastp/fastp/0.19.5+galaxy1: report_html

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/fastp/fastp/0.19.5+galaxy1: out1

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/snpeff/snpEff_build_gb/4.3+T.galaxy4: output_fasta

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/snpeff/snpEff_build_gb/4.3+T.galaxy4: snpeff_output

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/multiqc/multiqc/1.7.1: html_report

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/devteam/bowtie2/bowtie2/2.3.4.3+galaxy0: mapping_stats

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/devteam/bowtie2/bowtie2/2.3.4.3+galaxy0: output

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/multiqc/multiqc/1.7.1: html_report

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/devteam/picard/picard_MarkDuplicates/2.18.2.2: metrics_file

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/devteam/picard/picard_MarkDuplicates/2.18.2.2: outFile

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/multiqc/multiqc/1.7.1: html_report

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/lofreq_viterbi/lofreq_viterbi/2.1.3.1+galaxy1: realigned

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/lofreq_call/lofreq_call/2.1.3.1+galaxy1: variants

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/snpeff/snpEff/4.3+T.galaxy1: snpeff_output

 toolshed.g2.bx.psu.edu/repos/iuc/snpeff/snpEff/4.3+T.galaxy1: statsFile

Figure 7: Automated Best Practices Review for a workflow in Galaxy. Adding core metadata at an early state simplifies later workflow publication.

Currently WorkflowHub only registers a DOI in DataCite if the user [explicitly](#) clicks to first verify author names and title, and finalising that version of the workflow. This services as an important sanity check before making the citation data. WorkflowHub also permits “Work in progress” and private workflows to be registered, but these would not be eligible for DOI registration. In addition, the majority of the public workflows (~75%) have *not* explicitly been given a DOI, these don’t appear in DataCite nor OpenAIRE, and thus do not appear in EOSC indexing (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Idealised workflow publication pathway, exemplified from [Galaxy Training Network](#) and Intergalactic Workflow Commission (in reality GTN and IWC use two slight).

A **training workflow** (top left) is defined in any Galaxy instance, exported as a workflow definition (.ga), added to a [GitHub repository](#) together with documentation and instructions. Optionally structured **metadata** can be added to the same repository, as [ro-crate-metadata.json](#) as supported by GitHub actions build **HTML** to be published on the Web, e.g. Galaxy Training Network (GTN, e.g. <https://gxy.io/GTN:W00002>) or Intergalactic Workflow Commission (IWC). A **bot** monitors the repository and forwards the [Workflow RO-Crate](#) (bundling the .ga workflow definition with propagated and generated metadata as .json) to **WorkflowHub** (e.g. <https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/676?version=1>). WorkflowHub uses **DataCite** (transforming the bibliographic bit of the metadata to [DataCite Metadata Schema](#)) to register a **persistent identifier** (e.g. <https://doi.org/10.48546/workflowhub.workflow.676.1>). **OpenAIRE** catalogues [DataCite entries](#) which are then [added to DataCite graph](#)), and **EOSC ResourceHub** picks up this to make a [corresponding entry](#). In addition, both WorkflowHub and GTN allow the use of [GA4GH TRS](#) API to programmatically launch the workflow in any Galaxy instance, this is however not possible from EOSC, OpenAIRE nor DataCite, as these aggregators only have metadata and persistent identifiers.

As only the metadata is propagated to these aggregators, it is important that users verify the metadata is suitable at a global level, e.g. avoiding titles like “Use Case 4” which could make sense within a Galaxy’s user space or WorkflowHub’s organisational hierarchy, but not at EOSC level. Here we propose building “nudging” structures to occasionally suggest to a user they could make DOIs and participate in the scholarly knowledge graph.

Figure 8 illustrates how exemplar workflows for training and production can be maintained as source code in a GitHub repository, and be used both for the platform’s own documentation web sites and be source information for a workflow registry, which metadata is propagated through DataCite and OpenAIRE to the EOSC ResourceHub.

What is apparent from our exploration of these topic, which include developing automated bots and defining maintenance processes, is that there is a gradual loss of information, both for humans and machines, as the workflow publishing processes. For example, in the Galaxy Training Network, the page for a [particular workflow](#) (Figure 9) relates the workflow to its corresponding training for a particular scientific analysis, and gives detailed information about its execution, as well as different downloads. However, by the time the workflow is registered by OpenAIRE or EOSC, it is reduced to bibliographic entry of title/author/description, and its relevance for a particular scientific analysis is no longer clear.

assembly_with_preprocessing

assembly-assembly-with-preprocessing/assembly-with-preprocessing

Author(s)

Version
1

Last updated
Apr 22, 2020

License
None Specified, defaults to [CC-BY-4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Tags
GTN assembly

Features

Run Workflow in Galaxy Download

Tutorial

[Unicycler assembly of SARS-CoV-2 genome with preprocessing to remove human genome reads](#)

[Other workflows associated with this material](#)

Workflow Testing

Tests: ✗

Results: Not yet automated

FAIRness PURL
<https://gxy.io/GTN:W00002>

Download Workflow RO-Crate

View on (Dev) WorkflowHub

Figure 9: Workflow landing page in Galaxy Training Network. <https://gxy.io/GTN:W00002>

Zenodo

Publishing to Zenodo from Galaxy

Since 2024, Galaxy can publish individual datasets, full histories, and workflow invocations to InvenioRDM instances, including Zenodo (<https://galaxyproject.org/news/2024-05-03-inveniordm-integration/>).

Datasets and histories are automatically packaged in an RO-Crate prior to the upload. Just like WorkflowHub, Zenodo registers a DataCite DOI for each record, so this upload pathway means metadata is propagated from Galaxy through to the same scholarly knowledge graphs mentioned above.

Workflow invocations can also be exported to Zenodo. They can be exported in multiple formats, including Workflow Run RO-Crate (WRROC), a profile of RO-Crate which supports capturing details about workflow execution. This feature has recently been enhanced in collaboration with members of the FAIR-EASE project (Horizon Europe #101058785, <https://doi.org/10.3030/101058785>) to add further metadata about workflow authors,

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steps, and tools to the Workflow Run Crate (<https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy/pull/18820>). This will be published in the next Galaxy release.

Workflow invocation export in Galaxy has also been improved thanks to the WP5 materials science subgroup, who in late 2024 used their workflows to test whether they could successfully export a workflow invocation as a WRROC and then re-import it back into Galaxy. This identified some bugs in the export process, which have now been fixed, improving the reproducibility of the generated WRROCs.

(<https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy/issues/18927> fixed by <https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy/pull/19215>;
<https://github.com/galaxyproject/galaxy/issues/18995> fixed by <https://github.com/galaxyproject/gxformat2/pull/106>)

These features have impact beyond just the partners of EuroScienceGateway, as they can be enabled in any Galaxy instance. For example, the Galaxy instance at Naturalis Biodiversity Center in the Netherlands had the WRROC export feature enabled in January 2025, which will facilitate the use of WRROC to capture executions of workflows in the Biodiversity Genomics Europe project (Horizon Europe #101059492, <https://doi.org/10.3030/101059492>). There will also be impact in the FAIR-EASE project, as they plan to use WRROC export from Galaxy to capture execution of earth systems workflows.

The Galaxy Training Network offers [multiple tutorials](#) that complement these achievements and have been used in workshops like the [Smörgåsbord 2023](#) and [Galaxy Training Academy 2024](#).

Other options for publishing to Zenodo

Outside of Galaxy, any RO-Crate (including Workflow Run Crates) can be uploaded to Zenodo or another InvenioRDM instance using the `ro-crate-inveniordm` package (<https://github.com/ResearchObject/ro-crate-inveniordm>). This is achieved by converting the RO-Crate metadata to the DataCite Metadata Schema before uploading to the Zenodo/InvenioRDM API. The mapping between RO-Crate and DataCite metadata is decoupled from the rest of the code (<https://github.com/ResearchObject/ro-crate-inveniordm/blob/main/docs/mapping.md>), making it easy to re-use if other opportunities arise.

The legacy package `ro-crate-zenodo` (<https://github.com/ResearchObject/ro-crate-zenodo>) can also be used to upload to Zenodo but not InvenioRDM, and does not use DataCite as an intermediate format.

Changing workflow publishing practices

WorkflowHub Publishers and Journal Forum

The [WorkflowHub Publishers and Journal Forum](#) was established [Goble 2024] to bring together academic publishers for agreeing on policies and principles for workflow publishing. See Deliverable D2.1 [Soiland-Reyes 2024] for details.

FAIR Computational Workflows

The FAIR Computational Workflows guidelines [Wilkinson 2024] was developed by EuroScienceGateway joining the Workflows Community Initiative, as proposed in Deliverable [D2.1](#) [Soiland-Reyes 2024]. A book chapter is also in development based on this work.

Methodology for workflow publishing

Methodology for FAIR workflow publishing was explored based on practices for FAIR embedding of computational workflows found in the astrophysical community, taking as an example [Neronov 2020]. This paper was used as a case study of “FAIRifing” a scientific publication by retroactively converting references to workflow and data artifacts into reproducible references (Figure 10), implemented in an open source prototype (<https://github.com/esg-epfl-apc/astro-paper-workflow-parsing>).

Fig. 12. Zoom of the significance map of the sky region around GX 5–1 in the 20–30 keV energy band obtained from a selection of 44 science windows belonging to the GPS and GCDE programs carried out in 2013 with a pointing offset of less than three degrees from GX 5–1. This image can be obtained from the following [URL](#) ✓ (*ROCrates*, validated at 2023-01-12 14:28).

spectra found in examples makes it possible to generate the results described below online.

At the first stage of analysis, we determine the bright sources in the source field. We generate a mosaic image of the field and

$$\frac{T_{\text{in}}}{\text{norm}_{\text{disk}} kT \tau \text{norm factor } \chi^2/\text{d.o.f.}} \frac{\text{Flux (5–20)}}{\text{Flux (20–100)}}$$

Notes. ^(a) Flux ties, so we repo

Figure 10: An example of “FAIRified” reference to a computational workflow from a scientific paper.

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Data and workflow curation tooling

As a follow-up to FAIR computational workflow curation developments, a Swiss ORD funding was secured for collaboration with Solidipes (<https://gitlab.com/solidipes/solidipes/>) project, in order to provide efficient tooling for preparing, packaging, and validating computational workflow metadata for publishing in scientific journals.

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